

SUSTAIBILITY OF WORK LIFE BALANCE IN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCY

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INTRODUCTION

Work life balance is a person's control over the condition in their work place. It mutually benefit the individual business and society when a person's personal life in balanced with his or her own job. Work life is concerned with the impact of work on people as well as on organizational effectiveness, and the idea of participation in organizational problem solving and decision making. High emotional intelligence is very relevant for improving the quality of work life. In this respect, emotional intelligence acts in the following ways Emotional intelligence stimulates motivation, eases change, reduces stress improves communication and enhances rational decision making. It impacts people's ability to sustain both physical and psychological health. It enables to identify and express feelings in right way. It develops positive thinking towards self and others. It protects people from threats of psychological nature generated by criticism. It allows people to address fears by using reasons rather than avoiding them or allowing them to paralyses. It encourages people to be empathic, thereby understanding the feelings of others in right perspective

2. ABOUT THE COMPANY

The Oriental Life Insurance Company, the first corporate entity in India offering life insurance coverage, was established in [Calcutta](#) in 1818 by Bipin Behari Dasgupta and others. Europeans in India were its primary target market, and it charged Indians heftier premiums. The Bombay Mutual Life Assurance Society, formed in 1870, was the first native insurance provider. Other insurance companies established in the pre-independence era included

- ✓ Bharat Insurance Company (1956)
- ✓ United India (1906)
- ✓ National Indian (1906)
- ✓ National Insurance (1906)
- ✓ Co-operative Assurance (1906)
- ✓ Hindustan Co-operatives (1907)
- ✓ Indian Mercantile
- ✓ General Assurance
- ✓ Swadeshi Life (later Bombay Life)
- ✓ Sahyadri Insurance (Merged into LIC, 1956)

The first 150 years were marked mostly by turbulent economic conditions. It witnessed, India's First War of Independence, adverse effects of the World War I and World War II on the economy of India, and in between them the period of world wide economic crises triggered by the Great depression. The first half of the 20th century also saw a heightened struggle for India's independence. The aggregate effect of these events led to a high rate of bankruptcies and liquidation of life insurance companies in India. This had adversely affected the faith of the general public in the utility of obtaining life cover.

NATIONALIZATION

In 1955, parliamentarian Amol Barate raised the matter of insurance fraud by owners of private insurance companies. In the ensuing investigations, one of India's wealthiest businessmen, Ram Kishan Dalmia, owner of the Times of India newspaper, was sent to prison for two years. Eventually, the Parliament of India passed the Life Insurance of India Act on 1956-06-19, and the Life Insurance Corporation of India was created on 1956-09-01, by consolidating the life insurance business of 245 private life insurers and other entities offering life insurance services. Nationalization of the life insurance

business in India was a result of the Industrial Policy Resolution of 1956, which had created a policy framework for extending state control over at least seventeen sectors of the economy, including the life insurance.

CURRENT STATUS

Over its existence of around 50 years, Life Insurance Corporation of India, which commanded a monopoly of soliciting and selling life insurance in India, created huge surpluses, and contributed around 7% of India's GDP in 2006.^[citation needed] The Corporation, which started its business with around 300 offices, 5.7 million policies and a corpus of INR 459 million (US\$ 92 million as per the 1959 exchange rate of roughly Rs. 5 for a US \$,^[3] has grown to 25000 servicing around 350 million policies and a corpus of over ₹8 trillion (US\$145.6 billion).[¶] Awards and recognition== The Economic Times Brand Equity Survey 2010 rated LIC as the No. 5 Service Brand of the Country.^[4] Though in the year 2010 is ranked at 4, the organization is consistently among the top rated service company of the India.^[5] From the year 2006, LIC is continuously winning the Readers' Digest Trusted brand award.^[6] According to The Brand Trust Report 2012, LIC is the 8th most trusted brand of India.

GOLDEN JUBILEE FOUNDATION

LIC Golden Jubilee Foundation was established in 2006 as a charity organization. This entity has the aim of promoting education, alleviation of poverty, and providing better living conditions for the under privileged. Out of all the activities conducted by the organization, Golden Jubilee Scholarship awards is the best known. Each year, this award is given to the meritorious students in standard XII of school education or equivalent, who wish to continue their studies and have a parental income less than 60,000 Rupees

3. NEED OF THE STUDY

There is an increasing emphasis on the work life balance across companies human resource is viewed by most organization in a holistic manner. Work life imbalance and stress feed on each other. Happier employees are more productive and more loyal. Having an engaged employee in largely dependent on the ability of the organization to keep peace with changing employee expectation and providing a platform to strike the balance. The study helps to find the current level of balance the employees were able to maintain between their personal and professional life and also focus on the factor which improve the employees contribute in a greater level for their organization climate and employees perform better than disgruntled and stressed ones. Business world also see improved recruitment and retention. Additionally there would be lower rate of absentation customer's service. Overall there would exist a more motivated satisfied and equitable workforce which is a much needed one.

4. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- ✓ To study on work life balance in LIC agents
- ✓ To study the factors responsible for work life balance
- ✓ To suggests ways and means to promote work life balance of employees
- ✓ To examine in the satisfaction level towards fulfilling the family commitment.
- ✓ To analyze in the satisfaction level regarding fulfilling the organization commitment

5. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

To find innovative ideas to make the employees comfortable, happy and help them in having a balanced life and retain those employees from leaving in this highly competitive economic scenario. Work lives benefit the organization by increasing commitment, accountability teamwork, and improve morale and benefit the individual by improves relationship both on and off the job and reduced stress. It is very important to create a work life balance in an organization because people are the most valuable resource

6. RESEARCH DESIGN

In this descriptive research has been used. Descriptive research includes survey and fact findings enquiries of different kinds. The major purpose of descriptive research of the state of affairs, as its exists at present.

Research instrument: The research instrument in this study is a 'structured questionnaire'.

Sampling procedure: Convenience sampling is the sampling procedure used in this survey.

Sample size: Due to time and resources constraints the sample size was taken as 150 agents in consultation with the company and project guides from the total population 510.

Statistical analysis: The statistical tools used in analysis are Chi-Square test, Weight Average Method, Rank correlation, etc.

7. DATA ANALYSIS

Leadership	R1	Job itself	R2	Working time	R3	Salary	R4	Psychological	R5
24	2.5	49	5	26	3	33	4	16	1
24	2.5	25	2.5	38	4	43	5	22	3
44	5	25	2.5	19	2	26	2	36	4
22	1	36	4	54	5	21	1	18	2
36	4	15	1	13	1	27	3	58	5

R1-R2	R2-R3	R3-R4	R4-R5	R5-R1
d1	d2	d3	d4	d5
-2.5	2	-1	3	-1.5
0	-1.5	-1	2	0.5
2.5	0.5	0	-2	-1
-3	-1	4	-1	1
3	0	-2	-2	1

d1^2	d2^2	d3^2	d4^2	d5^2	
6.25	4	1	9	2.25	
0	2.25	1	4	0.25	
6.25	0.25	0	4	1	
9	1	16	1	1	
9	0	4	4	1	
30.5	7.5	22	22	5.5	
r=	0.525	0.625	0.1	0.1	0.725

$$\text{Average } r = \frac{0.525+0.625+0.1+0.1+0.725}{5} = 0.414$$

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In these factors the average rank correlation lies in the working time and leadership so the working time and the leadership are the main factors which leads to work life balance.

FINDINGS

- 48% of respondents are come under the age group of 36-45 years and 1% of respondents are above 56 years
- 48 % of respondents are under graduate and 1% of respondents are others.
- 74% responsible are male and 24% of respondents are female.
- 28% of responsible are having 11-15 years of work experience and 8% of respondents are having below 5 years of work experience.
- 40 % of respondents are got Rs10,000-15,000salary and 2% of respondents are got below Rs 6000
- 45% of respondents are strongly agreed to maintain a balance between work and personal life and 1% of respondents are strongly disagree.
- 73 % of respondents have to spend with their family and friends and 27% of respondents didn't have time to spend with their family and friends.
- 42% of respondents have time to spend in a week and 15% of respondents have time to spend in a week
- 40% of respondents are excellent in rate in rate of interpersonal relation with their superior and 10% of respondents are worst in rate of interpersonal relation.

- 51% of respondents are satisfied to meet all the family commitments being a carrier person and 2% of respondents are highly satisfied
- 91% of respondents say that they can difference the personal life and work and 9% of respondents say that they can't difference the personal life and work.
- 50% of respondents are satisfied with the relationship among their pees and 5% of respondents are highly dissatisfied.
- 70 % of respondents say that rewarded employee innovative ideas by the organization and 30% of respondents say can't rewarded for employee innovative ideas by the organization.
- 67% of respondents are saying the organization polices support to commitment both personal life and work and 33% of respondents are say negative.
- 41% of respondents are strongly agreed to maintain a balance between work and personal life is time management and 2% of respondents are strongly disagreed.
- 65% of respondents are say job stress affecting employee's family life and work and 23% of respondents are saying negative.
- 35% of respondents are very highly job stress affecting the employee's family life commitments as are employee and 11% of respondents are very low.
- 69% of respondents are say training programs in the organization to make acquainted with life and work culture and 31% are say negative.

9. SUGGESTION

- ✓ The organization must create awareness about the work life balance to improve the performance of the employee.
- ✓ The organization must improve the factor responsibilities for work life balance by the way of training.
- ✓ Employee perceive time management is a key factor in maintaining work life balance the organization can focus on imparting training on time management periodically so as to learn work training can also be conducted to improve integration stress management/
- ✓ The management must improve the employee education about work life balance in order to reduce the job stress
- ✓ Work life benefit the organization by increasing commitment accountability teamwork, and improve moral and benefit the individual by improve both on and off the job and reduce the stress.

10. CONCLUSION

Changing the economic and social factors have made the topic of work life balance salient to many workers and managers. The consequences of work life balance not only affect the employee but also his\her family and also the organization. Maintaining a balance in both work and life improve the individual both physical & psychologically making his\her efficient & committed. In an organization there are sizeable number of women employee, it is input to promote work life balance, it reflects in terms of attritation or poor performance or low employees will perform better than disgruntled and stressed ones. So lower rates of absenteeism and improved customer service.

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